

A Literature Review on Close Connections to Religion, Religiosity, and Human Psychology

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Abstract

Although many studies have been done on the Psychology of Religion, other research (Kirkpatrick & Shaver, 1992; Mak et al., 2011) has not found any link between religiosity and life satisfaction. As a result, the existence of a direct relationship between individuals' beliefs and attitudes towards religion and the satisfaction they receive from life is questioned. The effects of spirituality and religion on the emotional part is another area where results are conflicting. Some studies reporting a weak relationship between religiosity or spirituality and positive affect (Diener et al., 2011; Lun & Bond, 2013) highlighted the possible impact of the social structure provided by religious affiliation on experiencing positive affect. This was done to explain the findings of these studies. For example, some activities, such as prayer, appear to positively help in creating pleasant emotions such as gratitude (Lambert et al., 2009). In addition, recent research has shown that transcendent emotions such as curiosity, hope, love, and forgiveness play a role in mediating the link between religious practice and general happiness (Van Cappellen et al., 2016). According to the findings of these studies, religiosity plays a key role in producing happy feelings (Fredrickson, 2002). Also, Ramsay et al. (2019), another important mechanism that can explain the relationship between religiosity and well-being is emotional regulation. This mechanism involves functional modulation of emotional states in response to the demands of the environment. Individuals who practice religion often are more likely to become accustomed to the cognitive reappraisal process. This is because religion trains people to constantly reevaluate emotional events in their lives. Vishkin et al. (2016) have recently supplied evidence that these hypotheses are correct even among people of different religions (Vishkin et al., 2019). In this article, we tried to supply literature

support to decide whether there is a relationship between religiosity or spirituality and positive or negative affect, and if so, what it is.

Keywords: *Religion, Religiosity, Human Psychology, Close Links to Religion*

1. Introduction

Other studies have failed to report an association between religiosity or spirituality and positive or negative affect (Fabricatore et al., 2000), suggesting no significant association between greater religious involvement and spiritual integration and one's emotional experience. It is likely that he manages the inconsistency of results in the research . The terms "religiousness" and "spirituality" have each been defined and measured in many ways in research. Multiple and divergent indicators of a person's religion and spirituality have been associated with SWB, which at least partially explains the conflicting evidence found (Lun & Bond, 2013). We argue that there are three main general flaws in this research area and that the literature on the relationship between religiosity and spirituality has not yet achieved consistent results (Lun & Bond, 2013; Kim- Prieto & Miller, 2018). This is because there were three main general flaws in the research.

2. Defining Religiosity in Relation to Spirituality

First, the theoretical framework used to define and measure religiosity and spirituality in relation to it has often been overly broad. Also, it typically focused only on the cognitive or affective dimension, which has led to under-exploration of the subject (Lim and Putnam , 2010). To circumvent this limitation, it was necessary in this study to clarify the theoretical reference model on religiosity and spirituality as it includes both a cognitive and affective part (Diener , 1984; Luhmann , 2017; Diener et al. 2018). It is also important to evaluate the balance between life satisfaction and positive and negative affect. In addition, the cognitive part was found to predict

SL significantly more than the emotional part (Diener , 1984; Luhmann , 2017; Diener et al., 1985; Watson et al., 1988; Luhmann et al., 2012a,b).

3. Examining Religiosity in Terms of Religious Identity

Second, the concepts of religiosity and spirituality, although intertwined , appear to be separate in the literature (Zinnbauer et al., 1999; Hill and Pargament , 2008), and research has generally addressed only one of the two constructs and its link with religion. (Fabricatore et al., 2000; Lun and Bond, 2013; Kim- Prieto and Miller, 2018). It is likely that making such a fundamental difference does not help you understand how religion and spirituality differ in their connection to various aspects of religion. In this study, we examine religiosity in terms of religious identity. This concept expresses the extent to which individuals see their own religious beliefs, practices and belonging to the community at the center of the representation they have of themselves and that they want to give outside themselves (Lopez et al., 2011). Instead, spirituality was conceptualized as the human need for transcendence, reflection, togetherness, and the search for meaning in one's life (King & Boyatzis , 2015). Two independent path analysis models were used to explore and confirm the various roles that religion and spirituality play in relation to SWB.

4. Two Extremes on the Certainty of Faith Dimension (i.e., Weakly Religious and Confidently Non-Religious)

Third, we found that the categorization of religious experience reported at a more subjective level was not at all consistent (Galen and Kloet , 2011; Kitchens and Phillips, 2018). Those with low certainty in their beliefs (low or weakly religious) and those who lacked complete certainty in their beliefs (wholly non-religious or atheists) were combined into a single group in a number of studies. Two extremes in the certainty of belief dimension (i.e., weakly religious and confidently non-

religious). Because of this classification, the results obtained have been difficult to compare. Following the advice made by Galen and Kloet (2011), it would be correct to separate the respondents according to their religious status. It has been proper to do this without combining those who are not entirely religious with those who are unsure of their religious affiliation.

5. Components and Procedures

Historically, science and religion have often gone head-to-head. But the hostility in the argument disappears if we separate theology, which includes ideas about the nature of God, the creation of the cosmos, and other such matters, from the everyday practice of religious belief . What stays is a collection of traditions, practices, and feelings that are in themselves the product of many trials. These experiments, conducted in the messy environment of life as opposed to sterile laboratories, led to the design of what we might call spiritual technologies for thousands of years. These technologies consist of tools and processes aimed at calming, moving, persuading, or otherwise manipulating the mind. And research on these technologies has shown that some aspects of religious rituals , even when separated from a spiritual belief environment, can still alter individuals' brains in quantitative ways that psychologists look for.

meditation , even for a short time , results in increased levels of kindness in these individuals. After just eight weeks of training with a Buddhist lama, fifty percent of the individuals we randomly assigned to meditate each day meditated without being asked to help an unknown person in distress. Only 16% of non-meditators reported experiencing the same thing (Actually, the seeming stranger was an actor we hired to use crutches and wear a foot cast that can be removed when searching for a seat in a crowded area), But the compassion wasn't just random. people ; reaching out to his enemies. Another study found that after three weeks of meditation , most participants avoided taking revenge on someone who had insulted them. This contrasted with most people in

the control group who did not meditate . After seeing such powerful effects, members of my team began investigating further links between our past work and current religious practices.

has been extensive research on gratitude, which is considered an essential ingredient in various religious rituals . A prayer of thanksgiving called Modeh Ani is said by Jews every morning when they first open their eyes . Grace is often sung by Christians before meals. Our research revealed that even in a non-religious setting, the simple act of expressing gratitude makes individuals more morally upright. In a study in which participants had an opportunity to increase their earnings by deceiving others about coin flip results, most respondents (53 percent) lied about the results. However, when participants were asked to reflect their gratitude first, this number decreased significantly. Only 27% of these people made the decision to lie. Whether gratitude is directed at a particular person, universe, or God, people tend to be more helpful, charitable, and even patient when they are in a state of gratitude.

Even inconspicuous activities, such as moving in rhythm with one another, can have a significant impact on the mind.

We find synchronicity in almost every religion in the world:

Buddhists and Hindus often sing together while praying; Christians and Muslims often kneel and stand in harmony during worship; and Jews often shrug or rock back and forth as they pray together. These behaviors are only superficial manifestations of a deeper purpose to connect. To better understand how it worked, a group of people who had never met before, sitting across from each other at a table, put on their headphones and then touched a sensor on the table in front of them. For some of these couples, the progression of tones was the same, meaning that over time they would tap their palms together. Others got random ones, meaning their hand movements would not be coordinated with the others. We then produced a scenario in which one member from each couple was forced to perform

a laborious and time-consuming activity. Those who moved their hands in unison reported not only feeling more connected and compassionate with their currently working partner, but also fifty percent decided to help their partner, a significant increase from eighteen.

The way these practices use our body and thought systems has the potential to increase the pleasures we experience in life and reduce pain. Certain aspects of religious mourning rituals integrate components that science has recently identified as having the ability to reduce feelings of sadness. The simple act of increasing hope that we will be healed can accelerate the natural healing process that takes place in our bodies when we take part in healing rituals. Religions have not only discovered these psychological impulses and adjustments long before scientists stepped on the scene but have also pieced them together in complex ways that the scientific community can learn from.

amazement at finding evidence of the advantages of religion with colleagues is a testament to our arrogance. It was formed from a common assumption among scholars, namely, that all religions are based on superstitions and may have little practical effect as a result. We are not the first to admit that it is unlikely that religion will teach us much about the nature of the cosmos or the biology of disease. But it would be unusual if thousands of years of religious thought didn't have much to offer when it came to developing strategies to help people cope with challenges such as birth and death, morality and purpose, grief and loss.

As we pondered over the findings of my own work and those of other researchers over the past few years, we became aware of the complex nature of the link that exists between science and religion. From my current perspective, these two ways of making people's lives better often go hand in hand and complement each other. It is not because I suddenly became religious or because I had a new duty in life to defend religious beliefs. We have no doubt that the scientific method is a miracle and supplies one of the most effective methods for testing hypotheses about the workings of the universe. As any good scientist would do, we simply follow the evidence without prejudice.

Rather than laughing at religion and starting psychological research from scratch, we as scientists should work to understand rituals and spiritual practices, the impact they have, and, where proper, to develop new techniques and therapies that are informed by these practices. To achieve this goal, one needs nothing more than an open mind and a respectful attitude towards the religious beliefs of others. If we don't, we risk violating our ideals. If we choose to reject this body of knowledge and choose not to take these spiritual technologies seriously as ideas and inspiration for research, then we are hindering the progress of science and limiting its potential to help humanity. We will only be able to find new ways to make life better if we talk about science versus religion, or one faith versus another, beyond the boundaries that normally separate us.

, suggesting a significant amount of correlation between these factors .

6. When it comes to anxiety disorders

However, scientific approaches to this issue are difficult and involve several dimensions. When it comes to anxiety disorders, there is a scarcity of available scientific data that requires further research. In this review, we consider research results on the relationship between religiosity and spirituality (R/S), paranormal beliefs, and mental health, including magical thought and anxiety disorders . Results for obsessive-compulsive disorders (OCD) and other anxiety disorders (excluding acute stress and post- traumatic stress disorder) are presented individually to assess potential etiopathogenetic and cognitive differences between the two groups of individuals. An empirical narrative review of the literature is presented here . This review begins with an introduction to the subject, followed by an overview of the most important and clinically relevant publications on religion/religion, personal beliefs, and anxiety disorders. Finally, a special emphasis was placed on the dimensional structures of R/S and possible treatment options.

7. Spirituality, Religiousness, and Religion All Go Hand-in-hand

Religion is a universal human endeavor that has an impact on a wide variety of cultural traits, moral understandings, and values. It also has an impact on human thought and behavior, as it offers solutions to questions about the purpose of human life.

Religion is a fundamental part of human civilization because it offers a holistic and empathetic perspective on human orientation in the world. The practice of dealing with the sacred space through ritual or non- ritual cults, interpretation of everyday and private experiences, harmony with social norms, contact with aesthetic and artistic expressions and symbols, as well as many other aspects of life, are embedded. This is to a comparable degree in the individual and complex system.

On the other hand, religiosity is an expression that encompasses many aspects of a person's religious beliefs and the way they practice these views throughout their lives. It is widespread practice in academic circles to distinguish between internal and external forms of religious worship. External religiosity reflects the more instrumental and utilitarian aspects of religion by supplying security and solace, sociability and the ability to distraction, status and self-justification, while internal religiosity reflects the internalization of religions' teachings and personal master motifs in religion. Intrinsic religiosity also implies the presence of personal expert motifs in religion. In previous years, there has been a greater focus on spirituality as a separate and distinct entity from religion. This independence is emphasized. It is argued that spirituality is a part of human experience, both intercultural and interreligious , being a complex, idiographic and multidimensional construct not strongly associated with a single belief system, church or cult.

8. Personal Beliefs and Ideas About the Supernatural and Magical

In addition to R/S, a person's individual belief system also relates to one's propensity to have supernatural and magical ideas. Supernatural beliefs are associated with unexplained events that challenge the fundamental constraints of scientific explanation. People who feel that they have some degree of influence over events that defy generally accepted physical rules are said to have "magical thinking." This is the meaning behind the phrase "magical thought", which relates to views on causality. Although complex, a significant positive association was found between religious belief and paranormal belief variables, and higher religious scores were associated with greater paranormal views. This correlation has been supported by a number of studies. However, it is seen that they have a significant impact on culture and social life, not only on religious/religious practices and personal beliefs, but also on the physical and mental health of individuals.

9. Religion And Spirituality Play a Role in A Person's Physical Health and General Well-Being

Numerous studies point to the possibility that religion/religion and religious activities can have a consistent and significantly beneficial effect on a person's overall physical health, life satisfaction, and subjective well-being.

This beneficial effect of religious/religious culture on human health is more readily clear among people who are under stressful situations or have physical illness. Therefore, R/S is believed to be an important coping mechanism in the face of challenging or stressful life conditions. The importance of religious coping mechanisms has been emphasized in a variety of contexts, including but not limited to:

- *deadly disease,*
- *cardiovascular disease,*
- *cancer ,*

- *pain and*
- *immunological and endocrine diseases*

For some people, having religious belief can improve their ability to cope with difficult life experiences, while for other people, having difficult life experiences can lead to a deeper sense of religious belief.

10. Spirituality/Religion and a Person's Psychological Well-Being

Over the past three decades, researchers have paid great attention to the link between religion/religion and mental health, and their findings suggest strong links between these factors.

11. Function of Various Religious Coping Styles

appears to have the greatest value in relation to a person's mental health seems to be specific religious coping techniques rather than the person's R or S beliefs in general.

Religious/religious behavioral manifestations that are functionally expressed through religious/religious coping can be seen in stressful situations. Healthy religious coping mechanisms are assumed to have a beneficial effect on one's mental health. Higher frequency of religious services, general religious participation, as well as prayer and biblical reading have been shown to have an overall beneficial effect and are associated with improved mental health. These effects could not be explained by any potential contemplative aspect of the religious activity being practiced. On the other hand, negative religious coping (i.e., wondering if God has abandoned someone or believing in a punishing, vengeful, or simply indifferent God) has repeatedly been associated with negative psychological adjustment, higher psychopathology scores, and worse mental state. . It would be proper to say the health status and treatment results here. This is even though negative religious coping occurs less frequently than positive religious coping. However,

although research on religious coping has become more popular in the past few years, most studies have focused on the link between religious coping and clinical depression. There are few studies associating this parameter with anxiety, and most of these studies were conducted on patients hospitalized for a physical illness.

12. Anxiety and Anxiety-Related Conditions

Anxiety is a human emotion that includes feelings of tension, fear, and inner restlessness. It is a physiological response that manifests itself in response to unknown or frightening events and is always accompanied by a physical stress response.

Both the individual and the aggravating situation (stressor) play a vital role in deciding the degree to which anxiety is triggered. The presence of trait anxiety shows a consistent tendency to react with a state of anxiety in anticipation of potentially dangerous situations. Therefore, anxiety needs to be thought of as a dimensional concept, where personality traits and adaptive stressors are both factors that contribute to an increased degree of situational anxiety.

Anxiety disorders are characterized by a long-standing, pathologically heightened and unfounded sense of fear. This sense of anxiety paralyzes both the physical and mental functioning of the body and leads to avoidance behavior. Anxiety disorders are often linked to an underlying psychobiological dysfunction. If left untreated, they can cause clinically significant pain that can become a serious limitation for the patient. In this case, the anxious response is neither an expected or culturally sanctioned response to the stressor, nor is it largely the result of social deviation or disagreements with society. Rather, the anxious response is the result of something not normal.

13. Concern About the Presence of Religious or Spiritual Practices

There is not as much research investigating the precise relationship between religion/religion and anxiety as for other psychiatric disorders. Considering this, two main hypotheses appear. First, it supports the Freudian concept that anxiety can appear through negative religious conflicts and that there is a positive relationship between religion/religion and anxiety symptoms . This hypothesis states that there is a positive relationship between religion/thought and depression symptoms. There is little research that supplies evidence in favor of this hypothesis, and most of these studies only point to a certain positive association between anxiety and extrinsic religiosity. There is only a positive relationship between negative religious coping and anxiety symptoms, which is also supported by two other studies.

The second hypothesis is that religion is negatively associated with anxiety and acts as a buffer against the negative effects of stress. This results in reduced levels of distress and even improved clinical outcomes for the treatment of anxiety disorders.

Results linking positive religious coping strategies (e.g., particularly regular church attendance) with lower anxiety scores were often replicated, while other studies report results of lower anxiety levels among more religious individuals in samples of both healthy and medically ill subjects.

Despite this, a large number of studies have been conducted and none of them have shown a significant link between anxiety and R/S. Surprisingly, Baker and Gorsuch found that there is a positive relationship between externality and trait anxiety, but there is a negative association between internality and trait anxiety. So, the percentage of volunteers in a trial motivated by extrinsic rather than intrinsic factors could potentially influence the trial's findings.

14. Spirituality/Religion and Obsessive-Compulsive Disorder

The specific relationship between religion/Self and OCD has been more extensively explored in the literature than the specific relationship between religion/religion and any other anxiety disorder because R/S is thought to play a role in the etiopathogenesis of this disorder. This is different from other anxiety disorders. Early in the research process, the idea was suggested that obsessive - compulsive disorder might be what's known as " ecclesiogenic " neurosis. According to the findings of Higgins et al., the proportion of patients in the OCD group who reported experiencing religious conflicts was significantly higher than in control individuals who did not suffer from anxiety or other types of anxiety .

A considerable number of studies have concluded that there is a link between religion/religion and certain OCD traits. Specifically, elevated levels of religiosity were found to be positively associated with subclinical OCD symptoms and cognitions, beliefs about the extreme importance of thoughts, intolerance to ambiguity, misinterpretation of the importance of thoughts, control (thoughts, perfectionism and responsibility, weaker insight, and more perceptual distortions). Higher levels of religiosity have been shown to be positively associated with the emergence of religious motifs in obsessive thoughts and compulsive rituals,⁸⁶ and this has been found to be the case even when people who hold different beliefs are compared. People who suffer from religious obsessions and compulsions have much higher religious scores than patients who do not suffer from such obsessions . These findings make it extremely tempting to conclude that increased religiosity, particularly an excessive desire for spiritual purity, may have a role in the development of obsessive -compulsive disorder. It is interesting to note that a considerable number of people who suffer from OCD also have religious compulsions. According to the findings of some authors, when a patient self-identifies as religious, the likelihood of being diagnosed with OCD by a clinician increase, which in some cases can lead to tautological consequences.

On the other hand, there is a lot of research showing that there is either no or very weak link between R/S and OCD.

Neziroglu et al. In striking contrast to the findings described above, a demographic study conducted by OCD has discovered a much higher prevalence of atheists and agnostics in OCD patients compared to those suffering from other diseases. According to the findings of our most recent study, most of the Religious/ Vision subscales did not show statistically significant differences between OCD patients and healthy samples. Only negative religious coping showed higher scores among the OCD individual.

Anxiety and OCD-related supernatural beliefs little research has been done on the function paranormal beliefs play in OCD and other anxiety disorders. The findings of the limited research currently available are equally contradictory; some studies show an association between belief in the paranormal and reduced anxiety or neuroticism, and others report either a significant correlation or even a negative one.

Having magical thoughts can be a sign of anxiety and OCD. According to most of the exploratory studies investigating the specific relationship between magical thinking and OCD, there is a positive association between magical thought scores and OCD symptoms in clinical and nonclinical populations. These studies were conducted with both clinical and non-clinical populations . It has been shown that magical thinking is often associated with obsessive - compulsive symptoms and certain symptoms commonly met in OCD patients. Some of these symptoms include neutralizing behavior, perceptual distortions, and thought-action fusion. In addition, individuals with OCD were found to have higher scores on instruments measuring magical thinking than healthy controls or patients with other anxiety disorders. It has also been shown that thinking of magic can accurately predict a bad outcome in OCD patients. It is interesting to note that patients suffering from religious obsessions and compulsions display much higher levels of magical thinking than individuals who do not suffer from such obsessions .

On the other hand, little research has been done to examine the link between magical thinking and other types of anxiety disorders. Only two studies can be discovered when searching the relevant literature . In the first study, magical thought scores did not differ significantly between those with

OCD and those with generalized anxiety disorder. On the other hand, the OCD group showed considerably higher scores than the healthy sample. Patients suffering from panic disorder reported much lower levels of magical thoughts compared to OCD patients in the second study. It was discovered that those with panic disorder scored comparable to healthy control groups.

The latest research has revealed that individuals with OCD , people with other anxiety disorders, and healthy controls do not differ significantly from each other in magical thinking traits.

In addition , we hypothesized that inclusion of four OCD -specific questions in the original magical thought scale questionnaire would result in higher magical thought scores in OCD patients, consistent with the findings of earlier research.

Due to the prevalence of mental illnesses and their inadequacies, society is exposed to a significant cost because of these conditions. Children and adolescents make up a quarter of the world's population, and a significant percentage of them begin to show signs of mental illness at age 14. Some treatments have been found to be successful in lowering and increasing risk factors. The number of protective or preventive variables is important. However, there is still an urgent need to focus on mental health promotion initiatives such as religious education. The purpose of this research is to examine the key role that religious education plays in promoting positive mental health.

15. Argument

Education in many religions has the potential to contribute significantly to the emotional development of adolescents. Specifically, it can help develop healthier responses to stimuli through the internalization of religious morality; can help strengthen religious coping mechanisms that reduce the impact of stressors, improve coping skills, and encourage a less risky lifestyle; It can help raise awareness of religious beliefs and practices and their impact on the individual,

family and society, and can help promote connectedness, which can increase self-esteem and well-being. On the other hand, harmful effects on one's health, such as discrimination and social isolation, are also a possibility, especially for members of religious or gender-based minority groups. In addition to the negative consequences felt by members of religious minority groups, adolescents belonging to sexual minority groups may also be negatively affected by religious education. As mentioned earlier, adolescence is an important period for the development of one's personal identity and the formation of one's sexual orientation plays a key role in this period. Despite these unexpected adverse consequences, religion continues to play a key role in human existence, and if carried out correctly, religious education has the potential to positively affect adolescents' mental health. Schools are an effective setting for bringing together a large population of adolescents for the promotion of mental health, and it is important to reflect on the vital role religious education plays in mental health among those in this age group. Schools are an effective environment for bringing together large populations of adolescents. School-based mental health education and promotion strategies can maximize the benefits of religious education by emphasizing the effective application of religious education to influence adolescent mental health.

16. Source

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